

On the search for understanding car exterior designs' perception: A behavioral and psychophysiological approach

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Abstract In a very competitive automotive industry, new ways of innovation must be pursued. To understand consumers' reactions and to be able to innovate, one must understand how perception is held in a dynamic way and through the use of objective measures. Knowing that physiological and behavioral changes can reflect either emotional or attentional capture, the goal of this study was to evaluate whether car exterior designs could evoke significant reactions through the use of these dynamic and objective measures. Hence, different pictures of car exteriors were divided into two types: concept (C; non-commercialized cars, innovative designs), and non-concept (NC; commercialized cars), as studies have already shown that more innovative designs are cognitively more demanding (Carbon, Hutzler, & Minge, 2006). In a dot probe task, two cars were shown simultaneously for 500ms, followed by a dot, with participants having to push a button depending on which side the dot appeared on. Reaction time, electrodermal activity and eye movements were registered during the task. NC cars elicited higher mean electrodermal response and saccadic peak velocity than C cars. An exploratory analysis also revealed significant differences regarding different car shapes.

Keywords Attention, Emotion, Car design, Electrodermal activity, Eye movement

Introduction

The automotive industry is highly competitive, and to face this concurrence, car manufacturers must try to differentiate themselves from its competitors and elicit the interest of potential consumers. As technological development has evened the perceived differences among manufacturers in terms of quality and performance, it is extremely important for a manufacturer to find other type of solutions.

In order to find these new solutions, it is essential to understand what consumers want when using a product, as well as what are the different processes involved. They do no longer think about cars just for their sole function (i.e., transportation). Instead, they expect to fill needs, such as the pleasure of use or the matching of social values. In an ever-changing market, consumers want elements that stimulate their senses, and that are capable of being included into their lifestyles, allowing them to live an experience. They seek to be rewarded with psychological, symbolic, emotional and hedonic experiences (Schmitt, 2000). One solution may be to create more emotional products. To be able to do that, we have to study consumers' emotional reactions to products.

But what exactly constitutes an *emotion* when talking about an "emotional experience"? For Scherer (2000), an emotion is an episode with synchronized changes

of various components, including: cognitive processes, somato-visceral systems of adaptation and regulation, facial expressions, tendencies for action and subjective feelings. They are also evoked by stimuli with a particular significance for the individual (Fridja & Mesquita, 1994), and have a short duration (from seconds to some minutes; Ekman, 1992). Under a dimensional approach, emotions can be defined by two dimensions: *arousal* (referring to the activation level) and *valence* (positive, neutral or negative; Bensafi et al., 2002; Bradley & Lang, 2007). For instance, a picture can evoke a high arousal level and a positive (e.g., a photo of a skier in action) or negative valence (e.g., photo of a war scene).

Evaluation methods of emotion are classified by whether they measure physiological or bodily, expression or behavioral, or subjective responses (Bradley & Lang, 2007). Usually, in consumers and products' research, emotional responses are considered and measured as subjective responses. Therefore, for this study, we considered the use of physiological measures (see Boehner, DePaula, Dourish, & Sengers, 2007), allowing us to gain a dynamic perspective on the interactions with the product, without the consumer needing to verbalize or explain his sensations and reactions. Moreover, technological advances have made it possible to record these reactions in flexible, reliable, and non-invasive

ways.

These physiological measures reflect the autonomic nervous system (ANS) activity. This system is divided in two branches: the sympathetic system (that allows the organism to act, in order to be ready to react) and the parasympathetic system (that allows the organism to rest and recover its resources; Bradley, Miccoli, Escrig, & Lang, 2008). The most commonly measured indices are electrodermal and cardiovascular responses, with all ANS responses varying according to mainly reflecting sympathetic or parasympathetic activity or both (Mauss & Robinson, 2009). ANS activity is not exclusively related to emotional responding, as the ANS comprises a wide variety of functions related to digestion, homeostasis, effort, attention and others (Bernston & Cacioppo, 2000; Mauss & Robinson, 2009). Hence, it may not be clear when ANS activity reflects emotional or attentional processes, for instance.

Whether physiological responses have an emotional or attentional nature, their informational value is unquestionable. The way a car is perceived can influence consumers' behaviors, and, even though the global function of a car is unmistakable, the same cannot be necessarily considered regarding the elements that create a car (e.g.: doors, dashboard, handles, etc.). This notion can be explained by the central principle of Gestalt psychology, stating that "the whole is something else than the sum of its parts", "where each part points beyond itself and implies a larger whole" (Koffka, 1935, p. 176). Hence, if successfully achieved, decomposing the perceptual analysis of a car may allow us to understand some consumers' preferences and choices.

In the search of better understanding and measuring consumers' responses to car exterior designs, the goal of this study was to understand if it was possible to obtain and differentiate behavioral (i.e. reaction times and eye movements) and physiological (i.e. electrodermal activity) responses concerning car exterior designs. For this we defined two car types: *concept* (C; non-commercialized cars with innovative designs); and *non-concept* (NC; commercialized cars), presented in a dot probe task. Due to Carbon and colleagues' (2006) results showing that innovative interior car designs were more cognitively demanding and evoked more interest than more traditional interior car designs (through eye movements and pupillometry), and the innovative nature of the presented C cars, we expected to find significant behavioral and physiological responses at least regarding C cars.

Methodology

Participants

Thirty university students participated in this study: 15 female ($M_{age} = 21.87, SD = 2.92$), and 15 male ($M_{age} = 21.67, SD = 3.22$). All participants gave their consent, and they were paid for their participation. They all had normal or corrected-to-normal vision.

Figure 1. Experimental procedure used. Firstly, a fixation mark told participants where to focus their gaze. At the Cue, the car pictures were briefly presented, and the participant was expected to visually explore the screen freely. At the Target, the dot was presented, and the participant was expected to push a button depending on the side where it appeared. Finally, Recovery allowed the electrodermal activity to go back to baseline before the next trial began.

Materials

Tools

An Eyelink 1000 desktop was used to register eye movements, and an Affectiva Q sensor wristband was used to register electrodermal activity. Also, a questionnaire with a Likert scale (from 1, "I don't like it at all"; to 5, "I like it a lot") was given in order to assess participants' appreciation for each car exterior design.

Stimuli

Overall, 36 colorless pictures of car exteriors were used (18 C, and 18 NC). Regarding the computer task, the pictures of car exteriors were always presented two at a time. These pictures were presented at the *parafoveal vision*, which translates into a low visual acuity, being more sensible to emotional stimuli (i.e., it is the parafoveal vision that determines where our gaze will rest next).

Procedure

After giving their consent, participants started the experiment by performing a dot probe task, in which two cars were simultaneously shown during 500ms, followed by a dot. This dot randomly appeared at the same place as one of the car pictures previously shown, with participants having to push a button depending on which side of the screen the dot was presented (see procedure in Figure 1). EDA and eye movements calibrations were made only once per participant at the beginning of the computer task.

Participants were shown 18 pairs of C and NC pictures at the same time. After finishing the computer task, participants were asked to reply to a Likert-scale-questionnaire regarding their appreciation for each presented car exterior design presented. The side where each car exterior was presented, as well as where each dot appeared were counterbalanced.

Considered measures

In this study, we recorded reaction time, electrodermal response and eye movements.

Regarding reaction time, we expected participants to be faster to push the button when the dot appeared at the same side as the car exterior they were looking at.

Concerning electrodermal activity, it refers to continuous electric variations, changing from person to person, that arise when the skin receives innervating signals from the sympathetic ANS. Electrodermal activity can be separated into two types of phenomena: *tonic* (i.e., electrodermal level, referring to the person's global activation level, characterized by slow and stable changes) and *phasic* (i.e., electrodermal response; referring to fast and intense changes precise in time and stimulus-specific). As we wanted to measure participants' reactions towards different car exterior designs, we measured *electrodermal response* (EDR; phasic phenomena). A higher level of EDR would be associated with a stronger activation (*arousal*).

Regarding eye movements, considering the nature of our task and the duration of the pictures' presentation, we chose to analyze *saccadic peak velocity*. Also, this variable seems to be the most sensitive measurement regarding attentional state variations (see Di Stasi, Catena, Cañas, Macknik, & Martinez-Conde, 2013). Considering that saccadic velocity is related to the activation state in visual performances tasks (App & Debus, 1998), and that regarding data analysis, we only took into consideration the trials where the target (i.e., the dot) appeared on the same side as the wanted cue (i.e., the considered cue, C or NC), a bigger peak velocity was associated to a more important attentional shifting, translated into a stronger cognitive engagement.

Results and discussion

Our main goal was to understand if we could obtain physiological and behavioral differences regarding car exteriors. Globally, NC cars elicited higher saccadic peak velocity (showing a stronger cognitive engagement), and higher EDR (arousal), as well as higher ratings (measured by the Likert questionnaire) than C cars (see Table 1). Therefore, our results show that different car exterior designs evoke an attentional capture. Moreover, EDR results let us hypothesize that

the nature of these reactions may be emotional.

Theoretically, all NC cars were known to the participants prior to the experiment, whereas participants had never seen any of the presented C cars before. Therefore, these results may be explained by a familiarity effect being stronger than the "surprise" factor induced by innovative designs. These results go in line with Carbon and Leder's study (2005), that showed that a low attractiveness rating towards innovative designs could be improved with repeated exposure to those innovative designs. Moreover, Zajonc's (1968) exposure effect, where the mere repeated exposure (i.e., when the stimulus is accessible to the person's perception) to a stimulus enhances people's attitudes towards it, also helps to explain these results.

Considering a more exploratory analysis, car pairs were also organized by their shape. Categorization was made considering two parameters: *height* (low vs. high) and *outline* (angular vs. round). Results can be seen in Table 2.

We observed that low cars had higher ratings in the questionnaire, whereas high cars showed a higher saccadic peak velocity. In terms of low cars, NC cars were rated more pleasantly and evoked higher arousal compared to C cars, with the opposite pattern occurring between NC low and high cars. Regarding angular cars, NC cars showed a higher activation, as well as a higher saccadic peak velocity than round NC cars, with the last being better rated. Finally, round NC cars were better rated, but showed a significantly lower arousal compared to angular NC cars.

Even though a car exterior design is a concept too complex to just being divided by height and outline, we consider these to be promising results to further pursue and explore in future experiments.

In this study, we showed how it is possible to use physiological measurements (through electrodermal activity) and behavioral measurements (through eye movements) to differentiate consumers' perception regarding car exterior designs. Following the

Table 1. Significant results of C and NC comparison. (=): no differences; (<): lower.

	Objective Measures		Subjective Measure	
	RT	Saccadic Peak Velocity	EDR	Likert-Scale Appreciation
C vs. NC	=	<	<	<

Table 2. Significant results of exploratory analysis regarding car shape. (=): no differences; (<): lower, (>): higher.

	Objective Measures		Subjective Measure	
	RT	Saccadic Peak Velocity	EDR	Likert-Scale Appreciation
Low vs. High	=	<	=	>
Low C vs. Low NC	=	=	<	<
Angular C vs. Angular NC	=	<	<	<
Low NC vs. High NC	=	=	>	>
Round NC vs. Angular NC	=	=	<	>

exploratory results regarding car shape, further studies are being developed with the hope of shedding some light on this subject. The use of more physiological measurements is also encouraged, since it is the use of different indicators that will allow us to understand consumers' perceptions as well as to interpret their attentional or emotional nature.

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